

Intensive wheeled mobility workshops for physiotherapists and occupational therapists – a lesson to be learned

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Abstract The purpose of this study was to evaluate the impact of providing intensive large-group training on wheeled mobility self-efficacy and skill capacity among clinicians. Two instructors provided a total of 4 hours of wheelchair skills training to 8 groups of 15-20 clinicians, including a brief lecture, instruction, demonstration, and hands-on practice. Main outcome measures included perceived Self Efficacy in Wheeled Mobility (SEWM, score range 0-40), perceived Self-Efficacy in teaching wheeled-mobility (score range 0-24), and the modified Test of Wheeled Mobility (TOWM) ability score (range 0-8). Satisfactory survey post-workshop (score range 0-5) and Narrative reports were also collected. 106 clinicians completed the measures. Mean \pm SD of TOWM ability score was 5.34 ± 1.7 . Mean \pm SD of SEWM score was 31.08 ± 4.7 . Results showed a significant difference between Pre and Post workshop perceived Self-Efficacy in Teaching WM scores, $F(1, 81) = 42.97, P < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.35$. Overall workshop satisfaction survey mean score was 4.6 ± 0.3 . Many important and applicable insights were learned from what the participants reported narratively. Participants demonstrated improvements and acquired wheeled mobility skills that are considered more advanced using short training session. This study provides evidence for using an intensive training format as an effective strategy to increase clinicians' confidence and wheeled mobility skills' ability, preparing them to place greater emphasis on, and achieve better success in training future clients.

Keywords Wheelchair Skill Training, Physiotherapist Workshop

Introduction

Background

In Israel, according to the Commission for Equal Rights for People with Disabilities, there are 1.4 million people with disabilities, who constitute approximately 17% of the total population and 21% of the adult population aged 20 and over. People with disabilities often report loneliness and lack of friends, and a higher percentage of them have no one to rely on in times of distress. The number of wheelchairs provided to address mobility issues, mainly among older adults, is also rising.

Providing comprehensive skills training was found to be effective for wheelchair users. For example, , the Wheelchair Skills Training Program (Kirby et al. 2016), is a structured training

program reported in the literature, were an expert clinician provides personal training, typically requiring four to eight sessions of an hour or more.

The Israeli Ministry of Health trains clinicians who are authorized to prescribe a funded wheelchair for patients who need it. However, the Health Ministry's supervisor showed concerns that those who receive wheelchairs do not use them in order to improve physical abilities and self-mobility. This can be due to the fact that the physiotherapists in the community cannot demonstrate the wheeled mobility skills required on a daily basis, or that they do not see great importance in teaching these skills.

In a study conducted between 2008 and 2012, in the framework of doctoral studies at the Catholic University of Leuven, Belgium, a test of wheeled mobility (TOWM), was developed initially for people with spinal cord injuries who regularly use a manual wheelchair as their primary mobility device (Fliess Douer et al. 2013). The TOWM consists of a number of different tasks performed by the wheelchair user under standardized conditions. The test can serve as a guiding diagnostic tool in the rehabilitation process for people with a decreased walking function. Such an assessment can also provide feedback on the effectiveness of wheeled mobility intervention workshops.

During 2017, several workshops for physiotherapists and occupational therapists were initiated and supervised by the Ministry of Health, where wheeled mobility skills were taught from the modified TOWM test. The Ministry of Health has invested considerable resources in organizing the workshop, purchasing equipment, summoning the participants and more. The goal of this study was to evaluate the impact of providing intensive large-group training on perceived Self-Efficacy in teaching wheeled mobility and skill capacity among these clinicians.

Methods

Two instructors provided a total of 4 hours of wheelchair skills training to 8 groups of 15-20 clinicians, including a brief lecture, instruction, demonstration, and hands-on practice. The workshops were held in Assaf Harofeh Medical Center at the school of physiotherapy.

Main outcome measures included perceived Self Efficacy in Wheeled Mobility (SEWM, score range 0-40) (Fliess Douer et al. 2012), perceived Self-Efficacy in Teaching wheeled-mobility (score range 0-24, before and after the workshop), and the modified Test of Wheeled Mobility (TOWM) ability score (range 0-8). Satisfactory survey post-workshop (score range 0-5) and narrative reports were also collected.

The modified TOWM consisted of the following skills: Level propulsion forward (4x4), One hand propulsion (10m on a marked line), Ascend a sidewalk of 5cm, Descend a sidewalk of 5 cm, Up a slope of 10% (20cm), Down a slope of 10% (20cm), Up a slope of 20% (40cm), Down a slope of 20% (40cm).

Statistics

To determine the changes in perceived self-efficacy in teaching wheeled mobility pre and post workshop, one-way repeated measurement Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed.

Results

106 clinicians (out of 130, Male – 32, female - 74), have fully completed the measures. The sample statistic data (Mean \pm SD) are presented in table 1. Results showed a significant difference between Pre and Post workshop perceived Self-Efficacy in teaching WM scores, $F(1, 81)=42.97$, $P<0.001$, partial $\eta^2=0.35$. The gap between mean pre and post workshop score reflecting a significant increase of 18%. Important and applicable insights were collected from the participants' narrative reports, and these will be shared in the discussion section of this extended abstract.

Table 1. Mean (M) and standard deviations (SD) of the perceived Self-Efficacy in Wheeled Mobility (SEWM), the modified Test of Wheeled Mobility (TOWM) and Self-Efficacy in Teaching Wheeled Mobility (SETWM).

	Age (years)	SEWM (Max score = 40)	TOWM (Max ability score = 8)	SETWM Pre (Max score = 24)	SETWM Post	Overall Satisfaction from the workshop (Max score = 5)
M	45.03	31.08	5.34	16.3	18.9	4.6
SD	10.1	4.7	1.8	3.3	3.8	0.4

Conclusion and discussion

Participants demonstrated improvements and acquired wheeled mobility skills that are considered more advanced following a short training session. For example, in one of the narrative reported feedback, a physiotherapist wrote: "I learned skills in this workshop that I did not know existed at all. I understood that I have the ability to significantly improve the functioning potential of my patients". Another participant wrote: "It's so important to feel for yourself what a wheelchair user feels. I have learned how much I can help my patients and encourage them to stay active". Another useful comment was: "It would be good if we had some more time. I'd be glad to get full control of the wheelie myself. Maybe a follow-up workshop?" This study provides evidence for using an intensive training format as an effective strategy to increase clinicians' confidence in teaching wheeled mobility skills, preparing them to place greater emphasis on, and achieve better success in training their clients.

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